

THE IMPORTANCE OF DIGITAL EDUCATIONAL RESOURCES IN ORGANIZING THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS AND THE OPPORTUNITIES CREATED BY MOBILE APPLICATIONS

Madinakhon Alimova Iskandar kizi

"TIAME" NRU researcheradmin

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10034652>

Abstract. *This article discusses the possibilities of creating mobile applications in the organization of the educational process. The reader will also learn about the benefits of using mobile applications in education. This article is intended for use by school teachers, students and graduate students studying information technology in education, and freelance researchers in the field.*

Keywords: *mobile application, learning process, interactive, innovative technologies, education system, modern society, modern education.*

Currently, the ideal combination of educational system with innovative technologies increases the need for mobile applications. Such applications make it possible to organize the educational process in an informative, interactive and interesting way. It also attracts a wide student body, opens the way to the introduction of new services and helps to form a perfect communication with the student body.

In addition, the leading role in the implementation of the activities of an educational organization at any level is gradually shifting from paper carriers, such as printed textbooks and workbooks, to digital educational platforms and cross-platform applications. The obvious disadvantages of paper carriers include a high level of risk of data loss or corruption. The benefits of transferring the organization's internal document circulation to digital media are indisputable. Data can be stored in the cloud and viewed from anywhere while continuing to edit and grade. This situation played an important role in 2020 during the outbreak of the novel coronavirus pandemic, when all educational institutions moved to remote working and teaching, and all collected data about student testing and attendance. It was important to preserve the data.

A digital educational resource is a digital representation of photos, video resources, simulations and interactive modeling that describe dynamic and static models, audio components, vector and raster graphics, text documents and many other elements to organize the learning process. One of the subtypes of information resources is an electronic learning resource. Its functions include: creating, collecting, storing, processing, searching, extracting, copying, transmitting, distributing and using data used by technical means for their proper functioning.

In today's modern society, as the demand for the Internet and its tools is growing stronger, the importance of digital educational resources and mobile applications in enriching and expanding the content of the educational process in the field of self-education is also increasing, because mobile applications pave the way to bring it to a new level by making changes in the training system. Moreover, this approach works equally well for public education, for higher education, and for traditional education in other educational institutions, as well as for private instruction.

Learning with the help of mobile applications is very effective. The following can be cited as reasons for this:

- Techniques and software packages are integrated into one system and controlled from the user's device. In other words, educational programs can combine several classes or courses, and the student does not need to use different applications and resources;

It will be convenient to follow the development and dynamics with the help of mobile applications. Electronic statistics allow you to monitor progress, and tests monitor the learning process. Thus, applications for educational institutions can be made. The pupil's or student's electronic diary, class attendance schedule and other tools facilitate monitoring of the student's dynamics and progress;

One of the main advantages of mobile applications is that it increases the possibility of interactive interaction with the user;

Applications are also convenient in that they adapt to needs and capabilities. The user of the mobile application can study and use it whenever he wants, while traveling, on vacation, during a break between work. This opens up huge possibilities, customization flexibility and a unique offer.

Mobile applications for educational activities are not only beneficial for business, but also very useful for users themselves. In order for applications to be effective, its goals and objectives must be clearly understood. Then it becomes easier to understand what features to implement and what to implement.

Educational apps for schools, universities, and other formal educational institutions are slightly different from commercial apps. They are students' assistants, and at some points they have to replace the teacher. Typically, they perform the following tasks:

- to allow the student or reader to obtain additional information and knowledge, including through interactive communication with the application;

- acceleration of information exchange, improvement of interaction between teacher and student;

- creation of an educational community in which each participant contributes to its development;

- simplification of the assessment system and control over knowledge, as a rule, through tests and other assessment methods;

To modernize the educational process, attract more students or students and simplify the understanding of the received information.

Mobile learning involves the use of mobile technologies alone or in combination with other information and communication technologies (ICT) for learning anytime and anywhere. Education can take many forms: people can use mobile devices to access educational resources, communicate with others, or create content in and out of the classroom. Mobile learning also includes efforts to support broader educational goals, such as effective management of school systems and improved communication between schools and families. Therefore, it can be concluded that the mobile applications created or created for the modern education system of today's modern society - educational programs significantly increase the interaction between the student or pupil and the educational institution. Control will be simplified, the learning process will be more interesting, easier and more convenient, and the systematization of the knowledge base will allow you to update it in time.

REFERENCES

1. Доскажанов Ч.Т., Даненова Г.Т., Коккоз М.М. РОЛЬ МОБИЛЬНЫХ ПРИЛОЖЕНИЙ В СИСТЕМЕ ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ // Международный журнал экспериментального образования. – 2018. – № 2. – С. 17-22
2. Федотенко М.А.: Разработка мобильных приложений, первые шаги. // Лаборатория знаний. – 2019.
3. Melissa Ford: Writing Interactive Fiction with Twine. // QUE. – 2016. – 3 – 12 с.
4. Самохина Н.В.Использование мобильных технологий при обучений английскому языку развитие традиций и поиск новых методических моделей [Электронный ресурс] // Фундаментальные исследование журнал. – М., 2014. – No 6. – 592 с. – Режим доступа: www.cyberlinka.ru.
5. И.А.Штырова., Н.М.Виштак, С.А.Ремаренко. ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ МОБИЛЬНОГО ПРИЛОЖЕНИЯ ДЛЯ ВУЗОВСКОГО ПОДРАЗДЕЛЕНИЯ ДОПОЛНИТЕЛЬНОГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ //Современные наукоемкие технологии. – 2019. – № 2. – С. 153-157.